

THE USAGE OF "MAJOR" EDUCATIONAL METHOD IN THE TRAINING COURSE FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the use of «major» teaching methods in the training course.

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There is a constant need to learn new approaches and innovative methods in the process of improving the qualifications of public education workers. One such method is researcher A. The "Major" system proposed by Soatov is one of the complex methods that can be effectively used in education. During the application of this method, all mental processes of the performer (attention, intuition, perception, memory, thinking, imagination, speech) are actively involved. On average, 40 to 60 minutes can be spent using the method in training courses. How much time is spent mainly depends on the correct organization of the lesson and the activity of the audience. The method can be applied in the form of handouts or using information technologies. The peculiarity of the method application process is that other methods are used individually or in groups by the teacher, giving tasks to the listeners and listeners. They complete the task following the given instructions. They are evaluated or rewarded according to their activity and results. Since the Major system is a complex method, the teacher should demonstrate it first. In this process, the trainees will be introduced to the method during the allotted time and will learn about its importance. In order for the method to be used effectively, it must be fully and thoroughly mastered by the teacher. It is advisable to use the method in training in four stages.

First stage. In the first stage, the teacher informs the audience about the concept of memory, its importance and possibilities, and asks the audience what information is difficult to retain in memory. Listeners list factors that are difficult to maintain based on personal experience and observations. At this time, numbers are mentioned more often as factors that are most difficult to retain in memory. Then the teacher says that he wants to use in the lesson a complex method that serves to keep firmly in the memory the numbers that many people may have difficulty remembering. This will definitely be of interest to many listeners. Because listeners often face problems with remembering numbers in the process of learning. Therefore, listeners who know that meaningless multi-digit numbers can be easily memorized by the expected method will be more eager to learn it. In order to apply the method, the teacher chooses two voluntary listeners as experts. Expert listeners should sit together at a desk in the front row. The teacher gives them a sheet of paper with one hundred words, one for each of the hundred two-digit numbers included in the Major system. The sheet first shows in tabular form the consonants selected for each decimal system based on how similar they are. Experts look at the words hidden in the numbers. And the teacher tells the rest of the listeners to mix two-digit numbers voluntarily, and he tells the words hidden in the said number by heart. Here, the task of the experts is to observe and check whether the teacher is saying the words hidden in the two-digit numbers, which the listeners are mixing, by looking at the sample paper.

For example, if the listener named B says 11, the teacher should say "poplar", the listener named C says 35, the teacher says chain, and the listener named D says 64, the teacher should say bachelor. Because in the sample paper, 11 numbers are poplar, 35 are chains, and 64 are the word bachelor. Experts should check that the two-digit numbers, which are constantly being mixed up by the audience, are correctly recited by the teacher as soon as they hear them. At this time, the experts have to confirm the correctness of the words spoken by the listeners in a sequence, to which numbers the teacher said them correctly, and to say the correct word if they said it wrong, or to remind them if they don't remember.

Second stage. After that, the teacher starts using the method. For this, the listeners should voluntarily say the two-digit numbers they remember orally, and the teacher should write the numbers on the board. In this case, the teacher has to write down as many two-digit numbers on the board as he can remember in connection with the method until the audience says them. In my work, I mostly write two-digit numbers up to seven in the course of the lesson and tell them by heart after a set time. The teacher using the method should also write two-digit numbers, taking into account his ability. Only then, after the specified time, he can easily tell the two-digit numbers entered into the system. If the teacher memorizes six two-digit numbers by placing them in the system, he should stop writing the numbers after the sixth two-digit number is said. Because it is difficult to remember directly, it must be demonstrated that it can be easily remembered by putting it into a system and creating an unusual event in a sequence of six two-digit numbers. We mentioned above how to structure the event. Only the teacher should emphasize that the event consisting of two-digit numbers should be constructed in an unusual way. Scientifically speaking, because we have thousands of typical events in our memory, our habitual arrangement of events causes us to have trouble remembering the main event because we are distracted by many similar events in our memory. Unusual events are rare in life. Such unusual events, which involve illogical, strange or fantastic events, are stored separately in our memory and easily recalled when we need to remember.

Third stage. At the next stage, the teacher suggests to the listeners who should build an unusual event that should be built to remember, systematizing the numbers written on the board. The teacher will have to decide whether to compose, co-construct with the audience, or the audience to compose themselves. In such a case, it is better for the teacher and the audience to create an unusual story together. After creating an unusual event, the listeners must write down the numbers and words written on the board in their notebooks.

Fourth stage. At the last stage, when the appointed time has arrived, the teacher says the words orally by remembering the unusual events, and the numbers by remembering the words involved in it, or writes it on the board. This completes the process of applying the complex method. Listeners provide feedback on their impressions of the lesson. The teacher concludes the lesson by summarizing all the comments. In today's information age, where the scope of information is extremely expanding, a competent pedagogue's awareness of scientific knowledge about memory capabilities in the process of professional activity serves to form the ability of students and listeners to sort out the necessary information about science and retain it in memory in a rational way. The acquisition of such memory skills by students and listeners will not only improve the quality of education, but also benefit them in their future careers. In the process of formation of psychological service skills in listeners, we came to the following conclusions. In the process of forming the skills of providing psychological services, future pedagogues-psychologists

should acquire the following knowledge in the field of psychological counseling for the formation of psychological counseling skills: know the terminology, know the nature and features of the psychological counseling process; knowledge of basic psychological theories in psychological counseling; know the stages of psychological counseling; to know the basic theoretical and practical concepts related to the technology of psychological counseling. In order to increase the effectiveness of education in pedagogical activity, pedagogues should develop the following knowledge and skills. A skilled pedagogue should know the types of professional, personal, general cultural and special competence, have the qualities reflected on the basis of professional competence, master the types of pedagogical skills, be able to give advice to the learners to retain the necessary information about the science, using the memory capabilities efficiently, to the learners in order to easily remember the material, it is necessary to teach the rules of acquisition, relying on special mnemonic methods of simple and complex types. A skilled pedagogue can activate the mental processes of listeners by using the mnemonic method "Major" technology in the preparation of future pedagogues-psychologists for practical activities, the importance of keeping numbers in memory in the process of using technology, the stages of technology application, and the ability to form the ability of the listeners to learn and apply the "Major" technology in practice must have.

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